

ALEXANDRIAN MEDICINE AND SURGERY: AN INTRODUCTION*

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ABSTRACT – INTRODUCTION

A major step in the evolution of Hellenistic Medicine and Surgery resulted from the victories of Alexander the Great (356-323 BC), who conquered —more or less— the whole Eastern World, including today's Turkey, the Middle East, Iraq, Persia, Afghanistan and Pakistan, as also Egypt, Sudan and Libya. With the founding of new cities, Hellenic Science and Culture were firmly implanted in these countries with their ancient civilizations. In the same time scholars were able to collect the preexisting knowledge from the newly embodied or surrounding countries. An impressive cross-fertilisation took place, which became even more profound as all the gold and silver found in the cellars of the palaces of the Great Kings of Persia and Egypt, as also of all local kings, were struck into coins. This immense amount of money was thrown into the Economy and major new cities were erected. By founding all these new towns (for example at least 22 towns named *Alexandria* were erected), huge amounts of money were released into the circulation and finally reached every citizen. This caused an impressive expansion and flourishing of the Economy and even more. Poor people, who were unable before to reach a physician or a «Medical Centre», were now able to choose the best-ones. This resulted in a concentration of patients in major «Medical Centres/Schools» called *Asklēpieia*, causing an excessive accumulation of medical experience and knowledge. At least 400 temples of god Asklēpios, called also *Asklēpieia*, have been excavated; from Spain to the Himalayas and from Danube down to Ethiopia. The most important place of medical thought and practice became very early the famous Centre of Hellenic knowledge, the city of Alexandria in Egypt (*Alexandria ad Aegyptum*). Alexandria, founded personally by Alexander the Great in 331 BC, became very quickly the most important city. It was governed by a Dynasty which descended from Alexander's General Ptolemaios I, surnamed *Laghos* or *Sōtēr* (305-284 BC) and his successors Ptolemaios II and III. These three Kings founded and tremendously promoted both Arts and Science. They even built a Botanical and Zoological Garden, a so-called *Mouseion*, a Museum, which however served all Nine Muses, as also Medicine, and a *Serapeion*, a temple of the supreme syncretistic god of that era (bearing traits of Osiris, Ploutōn, Zeus *et al.*). Each of them was adorned with a vast library. The *Library of the Mouseion*, well known as the *Alexandrian Library*, became the biggest library of the whole Antiquity. This library was for more than 600 years (300 BC-342 AD) the true Centre of Knowledge of the whole Antique World and included about 900,000 book-scrolls. There most renowned Scholars, Scientists, Writers and Physicians of all possible cultural backgrounds could assemble to study and to teach. The prestige of having studied in Alexandria concentrated numerous scholars, teachers and students, making of Alexandria the greatest city of the Hellenistic World. A contemporary rival centre of learning existed in Pergamos of Asia Minor, though only after 250 BC, during the reign of Eumenēs I. However, the Ptolemaic Pharaoh jealously guarded the supremacy of Alexandria by forbidding the export of the papyrus plant or its products. It is said that because of this forced shortage of papyrus Pergamos developed a material derived from animal skin, subsequently called *Perghamēnē*, i. e.: *parchment*¹. Medicine flourished extremely well both in Pergamos (mainly due to its famous *Asklē-*

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¹ See LYONS & PETRUCELLI, 1987: 223. On ancient and medieval Medicine, see BAAS, 1889; ΠΕΝΤΟΓΑΛΟΣ, 1983; ΕΥΤΥΧΙΑΔΗΣ, 2001; MAJNO, 1975; WALTON, ²1979; CAMPBELL, 1926; KHAN, 1964: 64-74; ΜΑΡΑΣΛΗΣ, 1983; FRENCH, 2003.

pieion) and of course in Alexandria, due firstly to the *Mouseion* and the consecutive concentration of knowledge, and secondly due to the possibility of dissecting human corpses. As mummification of the dead bodies was practiced for centuries in Egypt it was easy to extend dissection as a *post mortem* examination. Anatomy and Surgery prospered enormously from these dissections, reaching their peaks with Galēnos of Perghamos, better known in the West as Galen (c. 130-200 AD) some centuries later. His treatises became the basis of medical knowledge for more than 1300 years. In our study we are going to examine thoroughly the principal Medical and Surgical Schools of Alexandria, with emphasis on the work of Celsus (Kelsos), Paulos of Aighina, Dēmētrios, Hērōphilos, Erasistratos, Galēnos *et al.*

I. ALEXANDRIAN MEDICINE

After the founding of the Museum with its famous Library scholars flocked from all over the World to Alexandria, including personalities like Eukleidēs (fl. c. 300 BC), Archimēdēs of Syracuse (c. 287-212 BC), Kallimachos (305-240 BC), Hērōn (fl. c. 62 AD), and many others. The same was true in Medicine which attracted all possible scholars. The most famous were Hērōphilos of Chalkēdōn, who flourished around 280 BC, and Erasistratos of Kea, who flourished a little later, around 250 BC.

HĒROPHILOS: He was the virtual Nestōr of the Alexandrian School and he was born around 330 BC in Chalkēdōn opposite Byzantium, today's Istanbul (Constantinople). He is considered as the founder of the Medical School of Alexandria. He was student of Praxagoras of Kōs and Chryssippos of Knidos. According to Galēnos he was a unique Anatomist and an excellent empiric practicing Physician. He wrote several books of which unfortunately only some titles have survived; at least three deled with Anatomy, one with the pulse, two with therapeutical subjects, another with commentaries on the *Aphorisms* and the *Prognōstikon* of Hippokratēs, as also a *Lexicon* on the Hippocratic vocabulary. Although only fragments of his writings have survived in the books of others, one can conclude that an immense amount of knowledge was added to Medicine and Surgery by his contribution. Hērōphilos described and named various parts of the brain (including the ventricles and the cerebellum), the nerves, the lymphatics, the eye, the duodenum, the pancreas, the parotids, the cardio-vascular system including the heart valves, as well as many other parts of the human body, as for instance the hyoid. Some of his discoveries still bear his name e.g. *calamus scriptorius Herophilii*, or *Kalamos Hērōphilou* in the East. He considered the brain as the seat of thinking (contrary to the ancient Egyptians who considered that the heart played this part) and in contrast to Aristotelēs also as the seat of the soul. In addition he was an excellent Gynæcologist and Obstetrician and described for the first time the ovaries (*ōphoron*) and the cervix, the ovaries being already mentioned by Hippokratēs. He had also described a birth of quintuplets (fifth lings). Hērōphilos was considered as the Father of Anatomy up to 1543 AD, when Andreas Vesalius (1514-1564) published his famous Anatomy *De Corporis Humani*. Hērōphilos was (definitely) the greatest Anatomist of Antiquity. However, about his surgical knowledge only very little is known. He understood much of the actual mechanics of Operative Surgery, but he was pragmatic in his use of these techniques². He postulated that the dislocation of the hip cannot be healed permanently, due to the rupture of the *ligamentum teres*, the intra-articular round ligament that carries the vessels to the head of the femur. He knew how to reduce the dislocation, but believed that due to the rupture of the ligament a relapse was always possible.

² See RUTKOW, 1993: 29; WILTSE & PAIT, 1998: 1904-14. Cf. also SCARBOROUGH, 2010: 235-60; YANNAKOPOULOS-SALILI, 2011. On Alexandrian and Byzantine Medicine, see also FOURNIER, 1933; GEROULANOS, 2007: 129-34.

He thought that the ligament was holding the head of the femur in the *acetabulum*. Interestingly enough, the *Encyclopaedia Britannica* has still much the same opinion³! The observation and description of all these parts of the human body could not have been performed without a systematic *post mortem* examination. Unfortunately his many treatises have been lost. However about his knowledge several authors have left written evidence like: Bakcheios of Tanagra, Hērakleidēs of Erythraia, Apollōnios Mys, Aristoxenos, and many others. That is how we do know so much about him and his significant discoveries.

FIGURE I: Hellenistic surgical instruments from the G. Tsolonidēs Collection at the Benaki Museum, Athens. On ancient surgical instruments, see BLIQUEZ, 1984: 187-204; MILNE, ²1970; SCHÖNE, 1903: 280-84.

HIS SCHOOL AND STUDENTS: From his students many continued his work, and illnesses like Ascites, Diabetes, Goiter, as well as many other Gynæcological Diseases were enlightened by them. Eudēmos became a famous Anatomist and Neurologist. He is mentioned by Galēnos [see VIII: 212] and Oreibassios. Hēgētōr is considered by Galēnos [see VIII: 955] as a Surgeon. Another famous Surgeon of this School was Apollōnios Mys who wrote 31 books on Medicine including Surgery. Other students wrote different medical books, e.g.: Dēmētrios of Apameia twelve books; Kallimachos (a relative of Hērōphilos) a *Compendium*, Kallianax a book with *Questions and Answers*; Bakcheios of Tanagra and Kydias commented on the *Hippocratic Corpus*; Chrysermos (the teacher of Hērakleidēs) wrote a book on *Pulsations* and Dioskoridēs Phakas wrote some 21 medical books. Zēnōn worked mainly on Anatomy and Pharmacology; Hērakleidēs commented on the books on Epidemics by Hippokratēs; Andreas of Karystos, another famous Physician who is depicted in Dioskoridēs' renowned book *De Materia Medica*, wrote at least three more books. Zeuxis and Alexandros Philalēthēs (the truthful) made out of the School of Hērōphilos a real legend. Kleophantos of Kea, probably a brother of Erasistratos and a student of Hērōphilos founded his own School. Gaïos and Dēmōsthenēs (surnamed also Philalēthēs) became Ophthalmologists, who performed cataract- and other eye-operations. Philinos of Kōs founded the Empirical School and Mantias is considered by Galēnos as a major Pharmacologist of his time. From the surviving texts of the School of Hērōphilos

³ Cf. *ENCYCLOPEDIA BRITANNICA*, 2006, 995: art. «Joints and Joinery».

rophilos one can conclude that Hērophilos himself had a deep knowledge of Surgical Pharmacology, Wound Surgery, Orthopædics, Operations' Techniques and he also applied modern Gynæcological and Obstetric Methods.

FIGURE II: A unique Ptolemaic wall relief, from the Temple of Sobek at Kom Ombo in Upper Egypt, depicting various highly sophisticated surgical and medical instruments (3rd Century BC); on ancient Egyptian Medicine and mummification, see FOURNIER, 1933; GHALIOUNGUI, 1963; 1965; 1993; GRAPOW, 1954-62; KAMAL, 1967; COCBURN & COCBURN, 1980; LECA, 1983; MAPABEIA, 2003: 163-78, 179-212; NUNN, 1996; & c.

ERASISTRATOS: The other major Alexandrian Physician was Erasistratos. He flourished at c. 250 BC. He was born in the town Julia on the island of Kea. His father Kleombrotos was a Physician and his mother Krētoxenē was sister of the famous Anatomist Mēdios. He studied Medicine in Kōs. His teachers were Chrysippos of Knidos, Metrodōros and Theophrastos. His brother Kleombrotos was also a Physician and probably the above mentioned Physician Kleophantos student of Hērophilos and founder of his own school, was also his brother. Erasistratos became famous for his writings [after the Byzantine *Lexicon of Soudas*]. He wrote apparently nine books, unfortunately all lost. However, at least twelve titles of his books have survived: two on Anatomy, two on causes of diseases, three on fevers, three on abdominal diseases, one on gout, one on deadly illnesses, and one on paralysis and paresis. Many other titles survived, but these could have been only titles of chapters of his books. His main field was (like Hērophilos') Anatomy and Physiology. Erasistratos is considered as the Father of Experimental Physiology. He experimented a lot and operated on criminals condemned to death. Strong pain-killers like opium were already available and were used in his operations⁴.

⁴ See CELSUS, *On Medicine*, I, *Proœmium*: 23 (cited by RUTKOW, 1993: 29-30): «Hērophilos and Erasistratos proceeded by far the best way: they cut open living men—criminals they obtained out of prison from the kings and they observed, while their subjects still breathed, parts that nature had previously hidden, their position, colour, shape, size,

FIGURE III: Surgical instruments from the so-called *House of the Surgeon* in Pompeii (before 78 AD). On the top copper cupping-glasses are depicted, in the middle forceps, two anal (endoscopes) and three vaginal specula (metrosopes). Down, different catheters, trocar, drainage needle and on the right a scissor.

This information of Celsus⁵ concerning both, Hērophilos and Erasistratos, is however not duplicated. They definitively used corpses of executed criminals for dissection. However if these body-openings were actual operations under pain-killers or vivisections is (after this passage of Celsus) not absolutely clear. The accurate observations of Erasistratos were extended to the structure of the brain, the intra-thoracic and intra-abdominal organs as also to the vascular system. He described the brain, its gyri and its nerves, with special emphasis on the *nervus acusticus* and the *nervus opticus*. As also Hērophilos, Erasistratos differentiated between sensory and motoric nerves, described the heart and the heart valves, the trachea and the epiglottis and explained its function, the bronchial tree and the bronchial arteries, the lymphatic vessels and the lymph nodes. He also related Ascites to a hard liver (Liver Cirrhosis). However, he mistakenly thought that the seat of the soul was the cerebellum. He was renowned for his abdominal operations, for his drainage of empyemas, and for the treatment of urethral strictures with an S-shaped catheter⁶. In order to reduce post-operative infections Erasistratos placed the hands before surgery in vinegar. Today we know that the polyphenoles, included in wine or vinegar, are extremely good antiseptics. One part of wine in nine parts of water kills in less than four hours *Escherichia Coli*, *Salmonella Typhi* Murium and *Vibrio*

arrangement, hardness, softness, smoothness, points of contacts and finally the processes and recesses of each and whether any part is inserted into another or receives the part of another into itself».

⁵ See CELSUS, *On Medicine*, I: 23; for a complete study, see SPENCER, 1935-38.

⁶ See RUTKOW, 1993: 29.

Choleræ, disinfecting by this way the drinking water! In case of urine retention he considered the placement of a catheter in the bladder of life-saving importance. He also used a pessary for the prolapsed uterus. Erasistratos was also the discoverer of the blood circulation. He believed in the connection of the arteries with the veins through invisible small vessels, today's *capillaries*, which he described in the lungs and suspected them in the periphery. He described that in the veins blood was circulating, but in the arteries *pneuma*. Unfortunately the word *pneuma* was wrongly translated in Latin with *air*. Thus all the following generations of Western scholars thought and still think that the Ancients believed that air was circulating in the arteries. However, *πνεῦμα* derives from the Hellenic words: *πνέω* and *αἷμα* = *air* and *blood*, i.e.: *blood* mixed with *air* and not *air* alone! In the Hellenic Language *pneuma* has several meanings as other words too. This is not uncommon. *Loghos* has for example 80 different meanings. Its meaning is varying from the term *word*, the term *reason* ... to the *Word of God* (i.e.: Christ as the incarnated Divine Word and 3rd Person of the Holy Trinity). *Pneuma* stands, still today, for *air*, *wind*, *breath*, *blowing*, *spirit*, *ghost*, the *Holy Ghost* (*Ἅγιον Πνεῦμα*), *intellect*, *wit*, *genius*, *mind*, and most probably in Antiquity also for *arterialized blood*. *Ana-pnoē* means *breath*, *pneusis* means *breathing*, *pneumōn* the *lung*, *pneumonia* the *infection of the lungs*, and *pneuston* is a *brass* or other *wind musical instrument*. Erasistratos puts it clearly that when the *pneuma* stops reaching the brain we cannot think any more and we die. *Pneuma* can better be compared in English with the word *spirit*. *Inspiration* that stands for both: *breathing in*, but also for *being inspired*. Erasistratos even postulated that the atoms of the body, the smallest unities of the body, the cells of today, required *pneuma* from the inspired air in order to live and to be activated.

II. ALEXANDRIAN SURGERY

The major progress in Anatomy and in Physiology in Alexandria changed the whole philosophy and practice of Medicine. However the big beneficiary of the huge expansion of the anatomic knowledge was Surgery. From a mainly trauma- and wound-care Surgery of the Hippocratic School, a more operative Surgery was developed. Unfortunately no major texts of these Surgeons have reached us and we all have to gather our knowledge about Hellenistic Surgery from referring authors of the Helleno-Roman, Byzantine or Arabic periods. However here we have three major authors' groups respectively that beautifully illustrate the surgical knowledge of the Hellenistic Period. Unfortunately they all lived much later.

1. AULUS CORNELIUS CELSUS: Celsus, a Roman citizen, was born approximately on the year that Alexandria fell in the hands of the Romans (30 BC) and he died around 50 AD. He was not a Physician but an Encyclopædist. He collected the knowledge of his time in a major series of books called *The Art*. Of this major *Engyklopaideia* only 8 books survived which are all about Medicine (*De Medicina*). Two of these books are dedicated to Wound- and Bone-Surgery. These two books are by far the best collection, which illuminates the Alexandrian Surgery. Here he describes many 1st Century surgical procedures including the removal of a cataract, treatment for bladder-stones and the setting of fractures. These two books were written 30-50 years after the Fall of Alexandria. However, during Celsus era, and up to 642 AD, Alexandria continued to be the centre of knowledge of the whole Roman Empire. Celsus' work contains detailed descriptions of the symptoms and different varieties of fever. He is credited with the recording of four of the cardinal signs of inflammation: *calor* (warmth), *dolor* (pain), *tumor* (swelling) and *rubor* (redness and hyperemia). However, as was said before, he

was not a Physician. He must have copied them from a Surgeon of his time, most probably an Alexandrian—one. The fifth cardinal sign of inflammation, the *functio læsa* (loss of function), is credited to Galēnos. Celsus also goes into great detail regarding the preparation of numerous ancient medicinal remedies, including the preparation of opioïds.

2. GALĒNOS OF PERGHAMOS: He is the second author who refers to the Alexandrian Surgery, he lived between c. 130 and 200 AD and wrote 300 books. Of these treatises approximately 120 have survived. Galēnos often refers to Alexandrian Surgeons. He particularly liked attacking them, especially when he was of a different opinion! He is considered as the greatest of the ancient Hellenic Physicians and his works influenced, for more than 1300 years, Roman, Byzantine, Arabic and Western Medicine. He contributed greatly to the understanding of numerous scientific disciplines, including Anatomy, Physiology, Pathology, Pharmacology and Neurology, as well as Philosophy and Logic. Galēnos was a highly skilled Surgeon, and he performed several surgical operations on human patients, including simple—ones, like *venæ sectio* and bloodletting then unknown in Rome. Many of the procedures and techniques that he utilized would not be used again for centuries. Of particular note are procedures that he performed on patients' brains and eyes. In order to correct cataracts in patients, Galēnos performed an operation that was similar to what is performed by contemporary Ophthalmologists. Using a needle—shaped instrument, he attempted to remove the cataract from behind the lens of the eye.

FIGURE IV: Pincer with finger—like ending, engraved with the latinized name of its Hellenic maker ΑΓΑΘΑΓΓΕΛΟΣ.

3. PAULOS OF ÆGINA: The third—one is the Byzantine author Paulos of Aigina (c. 625-675 AD). He lived 700 years after the conquest of Alexandria by the Romans and was also there when the Copts of Alexandria opened the doors of the fortification of Alexandria to the Arabs in 642 AD. Paulos' major offer to the Alexandrian Surgery is that he is not only describing the exact techniques, but he is citing the original texts too, as also the author that first described them. His book on Surgery is not only a masterpiece because of the detailed description of the surgical methods, but also a unique example for his medico—historical exact citations. Together with Sōranos of Ephessos, Oreibasios and Aetios of Amida⁷, who also cite with exactitude, we are offered through his works some very accurate information about many Surgeons that lived centuries before, as also about their surgical techniques and tools.

Archæological excavations have also brought evidence of huge amounts of extremely refined surgical instruments [FIG. I] or depictions of instruments [FIG. II] that correlate with the written sources. All this helps us to make a more accurate picture of the Alexandrian Surgery in its entire spectrum. A major treasure trove is also the *House of the Surgeon* in Pompeii (78 AD). There hundreds of surgical instruments were found [FIG. III]; some of which bear on them the name of their maker, e.g.: Agathangelos [FIG. IV]. This instance is recorded about one hundred years after the Fall of Alexandria in the hands of the Romans (30 BC), but they absolutely reflect the knowledge and the spirit of their Alexandrian ancestors [FIG. V].

⁷ On Oreibasios, see MOLINIER, 1851-76; on Aetios, see AETIOS AMIAHNOΣ, ¹1534.

FIGURE V: Two vaginal specula, with 2000 years of difference, identical to the ones from Pompeii. On the left from the Asklēpieion of Dion (Macedonia, Hellas, 2nd Century BC). On the right from a German textbook of 1847 [cf. ΠΑΝΤΕΡΜΑΛΗΣ, 1999; LYONS & PETRUCCELLI, 1987].

III. THE ALEXANDRIAN SCHOOLS

As old knowledge was put in question by the new discoveries in Anatomy, Physiology and consecutively in the rest of Medicine, major related discussions emerged. Even Hippocratēs' writings were challenged. The result was that different Schools appeared that would last for centuries after, namely the following: the Empirical School, the Erasistratos' School and the Dogmatic School. After the 1st Century even more Schools were founded like the Methodical, the Pneumatic and the Eclectic Schools; the last two Schools were actually an evolution of the older Dogmatic School.

THE EMPIRICAL SCHOOL: It was created by the disciples of Hērōphilos, with Philinos of Kōs (3rd c. BC) on the top. The Empirical School was based on ἐμπειρία, i.e.: *experience*. Empiricists emphasized the importance of physical practice and experimentation, or «active learning». Glaukias, for instance, from today's Taranto (2nd c. BC), who was Philinos' disciple and successor, formulated the so-called *empirical tripod*. This tripod was based on three main pillars: *perception* (αἴσθησις), *experience* and *practice* (πεῖρα) and *inspection* or *autopsy* (ἀντοψία). However the *knowledge of others* (μετάβασις τοῦ ὁμοίου), which could be applied in a new case was also considered extremely precious. After Celsus⁸, the Physicians of the Empirical School were excellent Surgeons and –except Phillinos and Glaukias– we do know Kleophantos of Kea (3rd Century BC), Hērakleidēs of Taras (1st Century BC), Zōpyros (1st Century BC) and Apollōnios of Kition (1st Century BC), who were also famous Surgeons and belonged to this same ancient School.

⁸ See CELSUS, VII, *Proœmium*: 40 ff; for a complete study, see SPENCER, 1935-38.

FIGURE VI: *Fœtus in utero*: from a 10th Century manuscript in Latin, based on writings of Sôranos of Ephesos (dating from the 1st Century AD). His writings on Gynæcology and Obstetrics were considered authoritative for many centuries.

THE ERASISTRATOS' SCHOOL: The students of this Medical School, the *Erasistratians*, continued the work of their teacher in both Anatomy and Physiology. They formed somewhat of a middle ground between the Empirical and the Dogmatic Schools. They were not as experimental as the Empiricists, nor as theoretical as the Rationalists of the Dogmatic School. They mainly used pure observation and showed greater interest in studying the natural course of ailments. They were making less effort to find new remedies. Their School was highly interested in Surgery and there are important signs that they were skillful Surgeons too. Several Physicians are thereby mentioned, like Stratôn (3rd Century BC), Ptolemaios (3rd/2nd Century BC), Philoxenos (2nd/1st Century BC) and Mênodôros (1st Century BC), and others. For the first time in the History of Medicine the word *surgeon* (*χειρουργός*) is *expressis verbis* used for a Physician, and in particular for Ptolemaios.

THE DOGMATIC SCHOOL: Later on both Hērōphilos and Erasistratos and their followers were included in the Dogmatic School. This was probably done by the followers of the Empirical School who included all other Physicians that –following the Aristotelian thinking and the Stoa– were trying to interpret medical problems with the logic/reason and not with practical experience. They were named *Λογικοί* from *Λόγος* (*loghos = word, dogma, logic*). A bit later even Hippokratēs, together with his sons, Thessalos and Drakōn, his son in law Polybos, and even Dioklēs of Karystos, were considered to belong to the Dogmatic School, although they had preexisted the founding of the School. It seems as if all Physicians that did not belong to the Empirical School were thrown into the Circle of the Dogmatic School because they were interpreting medical problems with Hippocratic, Platonic or Aristotelian theories. This School was mainly interested in Semiotic, Etiology, Physiology, Hygiene, Therapeutics and also Pharmacology. However their devotion to Anatomy made them also strong in Surgery.

FIGURE VII: Part of embryo– or cranioclast of Mēgēs of Karystos, dating from the end of the 4th Century BC and foetal hook, most probably from the same manufacturer. On the right reconstruction of the embryo–clast.

THE METHODIC SCHOOL: Two centuries later, during the 1st Century BC the Methodic School appeared. This School was founded by Themisōn of Laodikeia, a student of Asklēpiadēs of Proussa (1st Century BC), who is well–known for his description of Tracheotomy, and a successful resuscitation in the *via Apia* in Rome. Followers of the Methodic School mainly utilized pure observation like the Dogmatists. They showed a greater interest in studying the natural course of ailments, and again making fewer efforts to find new remedies. The Methodists formed somewhat of a new middle ground. The most famous follower of this School was Sōranos of Ephessos, who is considered today, thanks to his *Compendium* on Gynæcology and Obstetrics, as the «Father of Gynæcology» [FIG. VI].

THE PNEUMATIC SCHOOL: It is considered to have been founded by Athēnaios of Attaleia (1st Century BC - 1st Century AD). However the central doctrine of the School, which considered *pneuma* as the central principle of life and that without *pneuma* no life could exist, preexisted already since the 3rd and 2nd Centuries BC. Thanks to the Pneumatic School this theory survi-

ved long after the Medieval Era. After the discovery of the importance of Oxygen (1777 AD) for the respiration by Antoine Lavoisier (1743-1794 AD) the *pneuma*-theory is again very close to our patho-physiological thinking, as it puts in the centre of Physiology the blood enriched with air (today's Oxygen). Aretaios of Kappadokia, Archigenēs of Apameia, Rufus of Ephessos and the famous Surgeons Leōnidas, Hēliodōros and Antyllos (who successfully performed and described Aneurysmectomies), belonged to this very School. In their treatises we find descriptions of ligatures of arteries and veins, of improvements in Herniorrhaphy and urinary tract Lithotomy. They describe Tracheotomy, intubation of the larynx, resections of the lower jawbone, amputation of the breast for breast cancer, plastic operations of the breast, excision of the ribs and transplantation of rib cartilage for plastic reconstruction of the nose and the ears, as well as many others.

THE ECLECTIC SCHOOL: It was more or less a further development of the Pneumatic School, though with certain elements of the Empiric and the Methodic Schools. Some ones call it the *Second Methodic School*. It started during the Helleno-Roman Period, after the Fall of Alexandria in the hands of the Romans. This School tried to collect all positive elements of the other Schools and develop a new one more reconcilable. It is to be noted that again the members of the Eclectic School were also very active in Surgery.

IV. SURGICAL SUBSPECIALTIES

As Surgery was still part of Medicine more or less all Alexandrian Schools were practicing it. However in the introduction to the 7th *Book on Surgery* Celsus tells us that in the Alexandrian Era Surgery was separated from the Rest of Medicine and since this time we have also Surgeons as Teachers and Surgical Authors: «And later, when Surgery was separated from the rest of Medicine, it started to have its own Teachers. In Egypt the influence of Philoxenos was very strong. He wrote a very accurate book in several volumes on Surgery. But also Gorgias and Sōstratos and the two Apollōnii and Ammōnios from Alexandria and many many other famous men made important discoveries. And also in Rome there were some major Teachers in Surgery like Tryphōn the Father and Euelpistos. But if we look at their writings, the greatest of all was Mēgēs [FIG. VII], who together with the others have added a lot to their discipline and changed it to the better»⁹.

During the Alexandrian Era the development of refined instruments and very specific machines, gave also impetus to the development of specialized surgical tools. The development of new instruments and machines was so immense that the surgical specialty was for the first time divided into two major subspecialties: the *Surgeons* (*Χειρουργοί*) and the *Orthopædist*s (*Οργανικοί* or *Μηχανικοί*). The translation of the words *Οργανικοί* and *Μηχανικοί* into *Orthopædist*s is not absolutely correct, but corresponds best to the job that these subspecialized Surgeons were performing, e.g.: to repose dislocations of joints or fractures of bones with the aid of specialized machines. The development of these new machines, the *orghana* (*ὄργανα*) is something very specific for the Hellenistic Period, although already Hippokratēs describes some early forms of them, like e.g.: the *skamnos*, the *ambē* or the *bathron* (i.e.: the «extension bench») of Hippokratēs [FIG. VIII].

⁹ See CELSUS, VII, *Proœmium*: 3; for a complete study, see SPENCER, 1935-38.

FIGURE VIII: The Hippocratic bench as was modified by Aristōn the Senior and is still in use. Design from the J. Scultetus' *Armamentarium Chirurgicum* of 1653. Picture from the S. Geroulanos private collection.

The surviving texts speak very often of *Mechanical Surgeons* (*Μηχανικοί*). Andreas (3rd Century BC), Nileus (3rd Century BC), Molpis (2nd Century BC), Prōtarchos (2nd Century BC), Nymphodōros (2nd-1st Centuries BC) and Apollōnios of Thēra were renowned Mechanical Surgeons (Orthopædist). However, in the same time — as was already mentioned above — we read also of Surgeons, who were called Ὀργανικοί (*the ones using apparatuses*, i.e.: ὄργανα). Some of them like Apollōnios Orghanikos, were even famous in this very specialty. Others like Hērodotos, Aristiōn Senior, Passikratēs, Aristiōn Junior, Amyntas, Perigenēs and Hērakleidēs of Ephessos, were classified as *Orghanikoi*, without obtaining the related nickname like Apollōnios.

Unfortunately today we cannot distinguish between Surgeons named *Μηχανικοί* and the others called Ὀργανικοί. The sources are unclear and often contradictory. A bigger confusion is even created as Hēliodōros in the 1st Century AD says that the *Μηχανικοί* were not Physicians but the Ὀργανικοί were indeed Surgeons. Oreibassios (c. 320-400 AD) again — School colleague and friend of Julian the Apostate — writes: «Apellēs and Archimēdēs were not Physicians, but *Μηχανικοί*, who invented the ὄργανον, i.e.: the machine that lifts the boats with the mechanical power and not with the power of hands. The Physicians of this era reduced the size of the ὄργανον and made this *τρισπαστον* (= tri-partite apparatus) a medical extension instrument for the reduction of the dislocations of the joints and the fractures of the bones»¹⁰. We do hope that future research will be able to clarify the current situation and distinguish the difference between the two of them.

V. FAMOUS SURGEONS

Between the foundation of Alexandria in 331 BC and its fall into the hands of the Romans in 30 BC, several hundreds of Physicians are known of which at least 44 are declared since the

¹⁰ See OREIBASSIOS, *Coll. Med.*, XLIX: 23; For a complete study, see MOLINIER, 1851-76.

Antiquity as Surgeons [TABLE I]. Of the known—ones twelve lived in the 3rd Century BC, 7 in the 2nd Century and 12 in the 1st Century BC. Another 13 Surgeons are also known, but we do not know exactly the time they lived.

TABLE I: ALEXANDRIAN SURGEONS
3RD CENTURY BC
<i>Andreas of Karystos, Apollōnios of Memphis, Aristogenēs of Knidos, Bakcheios of Tanagra, Kleophantos of Kea, Molpis of Taras, Neilos or Nileus, Nymphodōros, Philinos of Kōs, Prōtarchos of Alexandria, Stratōn the Erasistratian and Xenophōn of Kōs alias Alexandrian.</i>
2ND CENTURY BC
<i>Amyntas of Rhodos, Dēmētrios of Apameia, Glaukias of Taras, Mantias, Philoxenos of Alexandria, Ptolemaios and Tharseas.</i>
1ST CENTURY BC
<i>Ammōnios Lithotomos (Urologist?), Apollōnios of Kition, Apollōnios Mys, Aretaios of Kappadokia, Aristos, Gorgias of Alexandria, Hērōn, Leōnidas or Leōnidēs of Alexandria, Mēnodōros, Sōkratēs, Sōstratos and Zōpyros.</i>
OF UNCERTAIN ERA
<i>Apollōnios Orghanikos (Orthopædic?), Apollōnios of Thēra, Aristiōn Senior and Aristiōn Junior, Dionysos, Diophantēs of Lykia, Glykōn, Hēliodōros, Hērakleidēs of Ephesos, Hērodotos, Pasikratēs, Perigenēs and Soklēs of Attikē.</i>

To the ones listed in Table I (*supra*) one should add the names of *Asklēpiadēs of Proussa, Euelpistos, Hērakleidēs of Taras, Mēgēs of Sidōn, Tryphōn the Father*, who lived during the 1st Century BC, worked however mainly in Rome. Most —if not all of them— were probably at least partly educated in Alexandria.

Of the above Surgeons the most famous were: Andreas of Karystos who constructed a new machine for the reposition of dislocations and fractures. His portrait is depicted in the Byzantine copy of *De Materia Medica* by Dioskoridēs. Neilos made another apparatus for the reposition of hip dislocations called *plinthion*. This apparatus was later on ameliorated by Hērodotos and Passikratēs. Nymphodōros built also, for the same reason, apparently an even better—one, naming it *glōssokomon*. Xenophōn of Kōs wrote a book on cancer and tried to classify cancer according to the anatomical localization, its form, its therapy and its prognosis. Dēmētrios wrote a Book on Obstetrics and Sōranos of Ephessos, the Father of Gynæcology, copied in his book, significant parts of the Book of Dēmētrios especially from the Chapter on *Dystokia*. On the other hand, Glaukias described the *empirical tripod* (see Section III, *supra*). Mantias is also depicted in the Vienna Dioskoridēs' manuscript and Galēnos cites his opinions on Tonsillectomy: «Tonsillectomy should be avoided at the time of the acute inflamma-

tion as a deadly *phlegmonē* can follow». Galēnos also mentions another Surgeon, namely Tharseas, who used a so-called «Indian» plaster. Celsus cites Philoxenos, who apparently wrote an excellent *Book on Surgery* and Gorgias who worked and operated on umbilical hernias. Finally, Mēnodōros had removed compressed bones of the skull and Ammōnios got the surname Lithotomos, the stonemason (the early name for the Urologists). He clearly states that big stones of the urinary bladder had to be trimmed before extraction. If not, the danger to injure the perineum would be extremely high.

FIGURE IXA: Reposition of a bilateral *mandibula luxatio*; two reductions of shoulder dislocation; two repositions of a hip dislocation; left a *luxatio suprapubica* in the middle a *luxatio ischiadica*. On the lower left reposition of a lower leg fracture. Dating from an 11th Century Byzantine copy (*Nikētas Codex*) of the commentaries of Apollōnios of Kition on the book of Hippokratēs *Peri Arthrōn* (*Codex Laurentianus LXXIV*, Bibliotheca Laurentiana, Florence).

However, the greatest book that has survived from these times is the 9th Century Byzantine copy of the commentary of Apollōnios of Kition (1st Century BC), about the work of Hippokratēs *Peri Arthrōn*¹¹. This book housed today in the Bibliotheca Laurentiana, in Florence, deals with dislocations of all possible joints. The illuminations are of a unique quality and most of the methods described are still valid today [FIG. IXA & FIG. IXB]. Apollōnios mentions that he had learned some of these methods from Zōpyros, who was practicing in Alexandria.

Unfortunately no other major surgical book has survived from these times. However, innumerable names of Surgeons, operation techniques, and surgical instruments that date back to the Alexandrian Surgery are named or described by Hellenic, Roman, Byzantine, Hebrew and Arabic authors. Here a huge field is open for serious research; it requires though, next to English or German or French, a good knowledge of Hellenic, Latin, Arabic and Hebrew, a combination that is nowadays extremely difficult. The best translations of Arabic or Hebrew

¹¹ See e.g.: ΒΟΣΚΟΣ, 2007: 96-293 & 344-565.

books on Medicine are in Latin, but unfortunately with the medical knowledge of the Medieval Period they present many misinterpretations. One must return to the originals, in order to perform a serious study. Translations in other languages are unfortunately only of superficial help, as most of them are for exact Research either biased or inaccurate, or even secondary translations from Latin.

FIGURE IXB: The four different dislocations of the hip (from a modern German textbook on Orthopædics). Compare the position of the right foot in (c) showing a slight rotation towards outside and the shortening of the leg, with the similar position of the leg and the foot in the Byzantine manuscript [cf. FIG. IXA].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, Alexandrian Surgery has reached — due to the freshly accumulated knowledge in both Anatomy and Physiology — a very high standard. Surgery was separated from the rest of Medicine. For the first time in the History of Medicine the term *Surgeon* has been used for a Physician (Ptolemaios) and the Antique writings provide evidence that several subspecialties existed indeed. We have «General» Surgeons, but also *Lithotomoi* (Urologists), *Mēchanikoi* & *Orghanikoi* (Orthopædists), *Ophthalmikoi* (Ophthalmologists), as well as Gynæcologists & Obstetricians.

Teachers in Surgery and authors of Surgical Books are also mentioned. Operations like Aneurysmectomies, Tracheotomies, Strumectomies, the Seton Technique for anal fistulas and many other operations were invented or ameliorated. Orthopædic extension beds or benches and other devices were created and surgical instruments invented, ameliorated or refined. Surgical medicaments were collected from the newly embodied or the other surrounding countries and greatly added to the Hellenic knowledge of that time.

It looks as if the apex of Surgery was reached during this Hellenistic–Alexandrian Period, tremendously influencing Helleno–Roman, Galenic, Byzantine, Arabic, Hebrew and also Western Medicine. Interestingly, the Alexandrian Medicine looks as if it was surpassed only after the invention of Anæsthesia! Unfortunately most of the writings of this glorious Period of recent Antiquity have been lost, to be able to prove with certainty this last statement.

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